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An Enhanced Method for Objective QoE Analysis in Adaptive Streaming Services

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ABSTRACT Evaluating Quality of Experience (QoE) is crucial for multimedia services, as it measures user satisfaction with content delivery. This paper presents an objective method for evaluating QoE in adaptive streaming services, using the commercial tool Video-MOS, which allows real-time monitoring and analysis of multimedia content quality across various platforms and networks. The method aims to provide a precise evaluation that incorporates both technical and subjective factors. This approach integrates multiple factors that influence the overall user perception of adaptive streaming quality, offering greater flexibility and performance, which could contribute to more comprehensive future assessment. The method is validated by a test plan that incorporates a variety of content and scenarios to simulate various network conditions. The results demonstrate the method's effectiveness in predicting QoE, highlighting the rebuffering frequency as a significant factor. In optimal conditions, specific content types can achieve a QoE score as high as 3.36. Conversely, under unfavorable conditions, the QoE may decrease by up to 1.42 Mean Opinion Score (MOS) points, which represents an 80% reduction from its optimal level. Although the rebuffering frequency has a substantial influence, a long initial buffer can have an even more negative effect on QoE, particularly under adverse conditions. Furthermore, adaptive streaming technologies, such as Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (MPEG-DASH) and Adaptive Bitrate Streaming (ABR) are integral to the assessment process.

INDEX TERMS Adaptive Streaming, Bitrate, Image Quality, Initial Buffering, Mean Opinion Score, MPEG-DASH, Quality of Experience, Quality of Service, Rebuffering Frequency, Rebuffering Period, Video Quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

OVER the last ten years, global demand for video streaming has increased dramatically, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Services such as Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, and Disney+ have seen remarkable subscriber gains, capitalizing on heightened Internet activity [1], [2]. Providing exceptional Quality of Experience (QoE) and specifically designed suggestions is essential to keep users satisfied and engaged. Maintaining uniform image and audio quality also encourages social interaction and enhances engagement with the content [3]. As these platforms continue to advance and enhance QoE, the consumption of on-demand video content is steadily increasing, cementing its role in contemporary entertainment [4].

Initially, QoE focused on Quality of Service (QoS), which measures network performance aspects like response time and reliability. According to ITU-T E.800 (International

Telecommunication Union), it refers to “the general effect of the quality of performance of a service, which determines the degree of satisfaction of a user of that service” [5]. Over time, QoS evolved into QoE, which emphasizes the subjective user experience with multimedia content. The ITU P.10/G.100 defines it as “the general acceptability of an application or service, as subjectively perceived by the end user” [6]. Factors such as system performance, human influences (e.g., age, mood), and environmental context, affect QoE [7]. It is commonly measured by the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) scale, ranging from “excellent” to “bad” quality. According to ITU-R BT.500-11 [8], this scale has a range of values between 1 and 5 where each number represents a feeling. Modern QoE evaluations use models depending on the availability of the reference signal (Full-Reference or FR, Reduced-Reference or RR, No-Reference or NR) to predict quality, but these metrics face challenges in complex

scenarios due to signal reference requirements [9]. FR metrics require access to the original video to perform a pixel-by-pixel comparison with the degraded version, providing the most accurate quality evaluation but demanding substantial computational resources and bandwidth. RR metrics use only partial reference information, such as specific features or extracted metrics from the original video. On the other hand, NR metrics assess video quality without any reference signal, relying solely on perceptual models and extracted features from the distorted video. This makes them ideal for real-time or large-scale applications where reference content is unavailable [10].

Adaptive streaming, widely used to deliver multimedia content, adjusts video quality and bitrate based on the network conditions of each user and the device capabilities [11]. Adaptive streaming divides the video into segments encoded at different bitrates, allowing real-time adjustments during playback. Protocols like Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (MPEG-DASH) monitor bandwidth to adapt quality dynamically, ensuring smooth viewing by hosting multiple versions of a video at different resolutions [12], [13]. This standard uses a dynamic Adaptive Bitrate (ABR) algorithm, which manages the quality adjustment adaptations necessary for adaptive streaming. Technologies such as Microsoft Smooth Streaming (MSS) and HTTP Live Streaming (HLS) ensure high-quality playback, even under fluctuating network conditions, driving the widespread use of adaptive streaming.

QoE is crucial for multimedia services, as it is able to measure user satisfaction when content is played. QoE takes into account factors such as content type, signal quality, subjective user expectations, and network conditions. In the case of content providers, QoE monitoring helps to resolve potential problem locations quickly and ensure high quality delivery, which increases user confidence and loyalty. However, network operators use QoE data to optimize resource management and reduce congestion. Furthermore, these data improve content personalization and improve user satisfaction.

Evaluating QoE in adaptive streaming presents several challenges due to the dynamic nature of these systems, which modify video quality according to fluctuating network conditions. Factors such as content type, signal variations, user expectations, and network variability make it difficult to establish consistent and reliable metrics [14]. Moreover, comprehending user perceptions of various content types requires advanced tools that align with subjective experiences. Real-time QoE assessment is further complicated by managing varying bitrates and buffering events, which can greatly affect user satisfaction. To address these challenges, innovative solutions must integrate both technical parameters and user perceptions to ensure high service quality and a positive viewing experience.

The primary objective of this research is to develop an objective method for evaluating QoE in adaptive streaming services. This method aims to account for both image quality and network conditions to provide a comprehensive QoE

assessment. The use of the commercial tool Video-MOS, which allows real-time monitoring and analysis of multimedia content quality across various platforms and networks using advanced Artificial Intelligence, plays a crucial role in this development. The Artificial Intelligence model was trained on a dataset with subjective quality scores, allowing it to combine objective metrics with human perception. As a result, the predicted MOS value reflects both measurable factors and individual preferences, enhancing its ability to capture the subjective nature of image quality.

The proposed method improves the existing Video-MOS tool by enabling a more precise and comprehensive evaluation that incorporates both technical and subjective factors. It facilitates dynamic quality adjustments based on network conditions, ensuring an optimal viewing experience for users. This is possible because the method is designed to detect resolution changes, bitrate variations, and measure the impact of buffering events and other interruptions on QoE. This approach integrates multiple aspects influencing the overall user perception of adaptive streaming quality, offering greater flexibility, performance, and accuracy for the future QoE assessments.

II. RELATED WORKS

Evaluating the QoE in adaptive streaming has been a hot research topic, with several models proposed to measure, quantify and improve the final user experience. General models are divided into three primary categories: parametric models, bitstream models, and hybrid models [15]. Each type of model has distinct methodologies for predicting QoE, using different sets of metrics and evaluation techniques.

A. PARAMETRIC MODELS

Parametric models estimate QoE based on network-related or packet-level parameters, without the need to decode the bitstream. This type of models are divided into two subtypes: packet layer models and scheduling models. Researchers applied a method that they called Mok [16] (considered as Mok model during this research) where initial loading time, re-buffering frequency and average rebuffering duration are key predictors of QoE, identifying rebuffering frequency as the most influential. In contrast, another work [17] emphasizes the relevant impact of rebuffering events, showing that early interruptions in the streaming have a greater negative effect on QoE than interruptions occurring later.

B. BITSTREAM MODELS

Bitstream models, such as those detailed in ITU-T Recommendation P.1202 [18], assess QoE by analyzing the encoded bitstream and associated parameters like bitrate, Quantization Parameter (QP), and Packet Loss Ratio (PLR). These models offer insights into how video encoding and transmission distortion affect the user experience. The model [19] conclude that users are more sensitive to rebuffering than to video quality degradation caused by lower bitrates or higher QP values. Similarly, [20] found that rebuffer events shorter than

TABLE 1. Metrics Considered by Different Models

Model	Rebuff.	Quality Changes	Initial Buffer	Encoding Quality	Memory Effect
[16]	x		x		
[17]	x	x	x		
[19]	x			x	
[20]	x	x	x	x	
[21]		x		x	
[22]		x		x	x

0.25 seconds have little effect on user satisfaction, illustrating a threshold below which rebuffering becomes less noticeable.

C. HYBRID MODELS

Hybrid models combine aspects of both parametric and bitstream models to create a more holistic assessment of QoE. Using both network performance metrics and bitstream analysis, these models can predict user experience more accurately. Hybrid models use performance estimates and buffer occupancy as indicators for decision making, applying control theory or stochastic optimal control equations to select the optimal rendering rate. The model [21] found that while the number of quality interruptions has less impact, maintaining a consistent bitrate distribution is essential to improving QoE. In [22] similarly noted that variations in bitrate can significantly affect user satisfaction, particularly in fluctuating network environments.

Table 1 presents the key factors influencing QoE across different models, highlighting the metrics each approach considers when evaluating user experience. The table outlines five primary factors: rebuffering, quality changes, initial buffering, encoding quality, and memory effect, that have been recognized as essential elements in QoE modeling.

D. OTHER KEY CONTRIBUTIONS

Recent studies have further expanded the scope of QoE assessment by integrating adaptive algorithms and optimization frameworks. The study [23] explores the use of both heuristic and model-based approaches for the optimization of QoE. Heuristic methods apply predefined rules, while model-based approaches treat adaptation as an optimization problem, factoring in both network and buffer conditions to maximize the user experience.

In addition, the survey [24] highlights key QoE factors, including QP values, loading delays, and overall user engagement. It stresses the importance of balancing technical metrics with user-centric factors to achieve a comprehensive QoE evaluation. Similarly, the research [25] proposes a Software-Defined Networking (SDN) approach that dynamically adjusts the streaming parameters based on real-time network conditions and user preferences, significantly improving QoE.

These diverse methodologies illustrate the evolving landscape of QoE research in adaptive video streaming. Addressing key challenges in this field is essential for developing effective solutions that can respond to dynamic network con-

ditions and meet the growing user expectations of quality. The emphasis on minimizing startup delays, rebuffering events, and bitrate variability is important to keep improving user satisfaction [26], [27]. Much work has focused on developing QoE models for adaptive streaming-based applications. Thus, the ITU-T P-1203 [28] series of recommendations proposes a bitstream-based parametric model for the evaluation of progressive download and adaptive streaming services. Furthermore, the ETSI TS 126 247 (3GPP TS 26.247) specification defines QoE measurement and reporting as an optional feature for client devices [29]. This allows them to measure and report various QoE metrics outlined in the standard, including HTTP request/response times, rendition change events, average throughput relative to playback duration, pauses, playback delays, and buffering levels, among others.

In recent years, hybrid models have also been designed for the evaluation of QoE in streaming. These hybrid models combine video quality degradations with global characteristics related to content playback, number, and duration of interruptions during viewing.

The Streaming Quality of Experience Index (SQI) [30] is one such example. The SQI model combines the quality prediction algorithms of FR metrics with information related to content interruptions. The model combines aspects related to content encoding, initial buffer levels, and interrupts.

VideoAtlas [31] is a machine learning model that combines several QoE features, including, for quality predictions, objective quality features, content rebuffering processes, and (short- and medium-term) memory-driven features of the user. The model takes into account the time between consecutive rebuffering events or between bitrate drop events.

In the broadcast and streaming domain, these models [32], [33] have been used as a machine learning technique for QoE estimation in MPEG DASH encrypted video traffic in 5G communication networks. The models make use of both key QoE indicators and network level QoS metrics.

Other contributions to related works include the NARX-QoE and DEEPQOE models [34], [35]. These two models introduce a new approach that allows real-time measurement of QoE by considering network issues such as delay or rebuffering, and content parameters such as video resolution or bitrate in content encoding. In particular, DEEPQOE employs neural networks and Round-Trip Time (RTT) parameter information as a crucial feature for real-time QoE measurement.

In addition, the TRRQOE model [36] presents a QoE estimator also based on neural networks that pay explicit attention to the temporal relationships between consecutive frames, evaluating the variance, to obtain information about temporal distortions. The TRRQOE model also integrates the features of individual frames to account for spatial distortions. The overall QoE prediction of this model is achieved by combining information from spatial and temporal distortions.

Finally, the QoE model [37] provides an adaptive streaming algorithm based on network bandwidth, buffer levels, and user-perceived quality values.

FIGURE 1. Structure of the method for video quality and QoE estimation, from input audiovisual content to final output results.

The analysis of the previously discussed models confirms that the features with the greatest impact on QoE evaluation are rebuffering, image quality changes and encoding variations. Understanding the impact of these characteristics is essential for optimizing adaptive streaming strategies and improving overall user experience.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the development of an objective method for evaluating QoE in adaptive video streaming using the MPEG-DASH standard. To validate this method, we will develop a comprehensive test plan that incorporates a variety of content and scenarios to simulate diverse network conditions.

A. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The structure of the method is illustrated in Fig. 1. It takes as input the various video playback resolutions, which are transformed into a Media Presentation Description (MPD) file through the process of MPEG-DASH content generation. This process involves encoding the original video into multiple quality levels or resolutions, and segmenting it into small chunks. The MPD file is then generated, which outlines the structure, the available quality levels and segment details for adaptive streaming. This file allows the player to dynamically select the appropriate segment based on network conditions and device capabilities, ensuring seamless playback across various devices and network conditions.

Additionally, the different resolutions are processed using the Video-MOS tool to derive all potential MOS values for the video. The method then evaluates the content playback, analyzing image quality and penalties. Ultimately, a file is generated containing the compiled data, including the final QoE value.

Following the development of the method, various scenarios were established to perform the tests and assess the collected results. In addition, to improve diversity, three distinct contents were examined in each scenario. This testing strategy aims to validate the method that has been implemented.

The contents selected for this test plan are presented in Fig. 2, where it can be seen that they present different visual characteristics. These content types exhibit significant different

attributes in terms of colorimetry, textures and object motion, with animated content characterized by uniform colors, video-game content featuring distinct textures, and real-life and science fiction content presenting more complex visual details and dynamic movement. Peach (Big Buck Bunny), Durian (Sintel), and Mango (Tears of Steel) are code names for different short film projects undertaken by the Blender Foundation¹. These projects are part of the Open Movie initiative and have been released under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 (CC-BY 3.0) license², which allows anyone to use, modify, and distribute the content, provided that proper attribution is given to the original creators.

The three contents have been converted to DASH format with the MP4Box tool, a multimedia packager available in GPAC framework³. The most important feature when generating the DASH stream is that the chunk size is fixed at three seconds. This ensures that the segments align precisely with the three-second interval set for the QoE analysis, avoiding non-exact fragment sizes and ensuring a consistent mapping between chunks and quality assessment intervals.

The diversity of the three contents is manifested in the wide range of Spatial Information (SI) and Temporal Information (TI). SI refers to the amount of detail and clarity in an image or video, encompassing factors such as resolution, sharpness and the distribution of visual elements throughout the image. Higher SI values indicate greater visual detail. In contrast, TI relates to the changes and movement between consecutive images in a video. Elevated TI values reflect greater variation between successive images.

Both SI and TI are essential characteristics for describing video sequences, as they significantly impact the assessment of video quality. Together, these factors are fundamental in shaping the overall perception of quality, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of both visual accuracy and fluidity of motion in video content [38]. Fig. 3 illustrates the SI-TI diagram for each content. SI and TI values are calculated ac-

¹<https://blender.org/about/>

²The content is released under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 License, available at <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>.

³<https://wiki.gpac.io/>

FIGURE 2. Characterization of the content type of the test video sequences.

FIGURE 3. Distribution diagrams of the test video sequences of Spatial Information and Temporal Information.

ording to the formulas outlined in ITU-T Recommendation P.910 [39].

Four scenarios have been defined with different network conditions that simulate the possible environments in which a video can be played. The throughput represents, on average across all content, the amount of data transmitted per second at each resolution, providing a clear measure of the video quality available for each content as a function of resolution. This data is taken from the downloaded MPD files. To simulate these scenarios, the Network Throttling development tool included in the Google Chrome browser has been used. This tool allows simulating different connection speeds to evaluate the performance of the developed method under various network conditions⁴.

While typically used for testing website performance, Network Throttling is also applicable to video streaming. Adaptive streaming protocols like MPEG-DASH rely on HTTP-based delivery, and throttling allows us to simulate conditions such as fluctuation bandwidth, packet loss, and high latency. These conditions directly influence the performance of adaptive bitrate algorithms, enabling us to observe how video quality adjusts, how the streaming player maintains playback stability, and how the user experience is affected by network limitations.

⁴<https://developer.chrome.com/docs/devtools/settings/throttling>

The tests were conducted using Google Chrome, the method itself is independent of the browser because the underlying adaptive streaming behavior is controlled by the ABR algorithm, not the browser. The experiments were conducted using a single-user setup to isolate the impact of network conditions on adaptive streaming behavior. Each test scenario was repeated multiple times to ensure the consistency and reproducibility of the results. Network Throttling simulates real-world network constraints, offering the tool to impact the network conditions on video streaming QoE.

In these scenarios, the behavior of adaptive streaming has been analyzed in detail throughout the content, as well as the specific parameters considered in the QoE evaluation Equation (2) developed for this study.

- **Scenario 1 (Optimal - 50 Mbps):** The video has the full capacity of the network, simulating a typical home Internet connection. This means that there would be no data rate restrictions, reaching the maximum download speed. The adaptive streaming ABR algorithm will select the optimal quality at all times.
- **Scenario 2 (Good - 5 Mbps):** The average data rate is high enough to support high video qualities, but with some limitations compared to the optimal scenario. Although the maximum resolution for all videos is not expected to be achieved, users would enjoy a clear and

smooth viewing experience, with minimal interruptions and good image quality.

- **Scenario 3 (Acceptable - 1 Mbps):** The network has important restrictions that limit the data rate. The adaptive streaming ABR algorithm will adjust by selecting lower video qualities. Although the picture quality would be lower at higher resolutions, users would still be able to view the content without prolonged interruptions, although some degradation in video sharpness and detail is likely to be experienced.
- **Scenario 4 (Poor - 0.3 Mbps):** Network limitations impose significant constraints, resulting in very low bitrate in some cases. The ABR algorithm would adapt by selecting the lowest available video quality to ensure uninterrupted playback. While picture quality would be reduced, the stream would remain stable, minimizing pauses and buffering. This scenario provides the minimum acceptable quality for video viewing, prioritizing stream continuity over visual quality.

B. ADOPTION AND ADAPTATION OF MOK MODEL FOR QOE ASSESSMENT

The Mok model serves as the basis for the approach and development of the proposed QoE assessment method, as it is one of the pioneering models focusing on QoS applications in adaptive streaming over HTTP. This is the case because most models, both recent and older, maintain the correlation of the parameters (T_{init} , F_{rebuff} and T_{rebuf}) with QoE. Moreover, the Mok model presents a linear structure for quality analysis, which can be easily adopted in Equation (1).

This model systematically investigates the interaction between QoS and user experience by analyzing network characteristics, including bandwidth, latency, and packet loss. Specifically, it incorporates essential metrics that are crucial for accurately predicting video streaming behavior.

To enhance the applicability and robustness of the model, Mok's framework integrates subjective experiments involving real users, thereby facilitating a deeper understanding of how varying network conditions impact the perception of QoE. These empirical assessments provide valuable information on the influence of QoS variations on user satisfaction throughout the viewing experience.

However, it is crucial to recognize that Mok operates under the assumption of stable network conditions and the absence of user interactions, such as pausing or fast forwarding, during playback. Although these assumptions may limit the precision of QoE evaluations, the model is widely acknowledged for its efficacy in analyzing user experience within the domain of adaptive streaming video quality.

The QoE is quantified using the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{QoE}_{\text{Mok}} = & 4.23 - 0.067 \cdot T_{\text{init}} \\ & - 0.742 \cdot F_{\text{rebuff}} - 0.106 \cdot T_{\text{rebuf}} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- T_{init} : Initial time from video download to playback, measured in seconds.
- F_{rebuff} : Frequency of rebuffering events, indicating the number of times the buffer reaches zero during playback relative to the total duration of the video, measured in events per second.
- T_{rebuf} : The total duration of rebuffering events, which is the sum of all periods where the buffer is empty. This value is considered relative to the total video duration, meaning it represents the proportion of time spent in buffering compared to the entire playback time.

Although Equation (1) effectively models the relationship between perceived quality and the three factors mentioned above, it exhibits a unit inconsistency. Specifically, the terms T_{init} and T_{rebuf} are measured in seconds, while F_{rebuff} is a dimensionless variable representing the number of interruptions per second. This could initially appear problematic, as QoE is a dimensionless variable. However, the equation is designed to address this discrepancy with the coefficients ($\alpha = -0.067$ expressed in hertz or inverse seconds, $\beta = -0.742$, expressed in seconds and $\gamma = -0.106$ as non-dimensional) adjusting the contribution of each factor to QoE in such way that the final result remains a dimensionless score. The three coefficients not only reflect the relative influence of each factor but also effectively normalize the input units, ensuring the equation yields a consistent measure of user experience.

The weights accompanying these parameters, along with these metrics, represent penalties derived from an ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) analysis carried out in [16]. This analysis demonstrated that F_{rebuff} (the frequency of rebuffering events) is the main factor influencing the QoE, with a weight of 0.742 in the final equation. Rebuffering interruptions negatively impact the user experience, as users find these pauses disruptive. In contrast, the initial buffering time T_{init} and the average rebuffering duration T_{rebuf} were less significant, with weights of 0.067 and 0.106, respectively. The analysis revealed that while users tolerate a longer initial delay for better video quality, excessive rebuffering results in a notable decrease in perceived quality.

The key aspect of this method lies in replacing the fixed value of 4.23 with an average of the MOS values, denoted as MOS_{avg} , which is obtained using the Video-MOS system. This average MOS_{avg} represents the overall perceived quality of the video content, as rated by users across various scenarios. Using MOS_{avg} allows for a more dynamic and accurate adaptation to the specific characteristics of each type of content being evaluated. This adjustment ensures that the evaluation reflects the actual quality perceived by users for different videos, rather than relying on a static value.

The structure of the implemented method is organized, following Equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{QoE} = & MOS_{\text{avg}} - 0.067 \cdot T_{\text{init}} \\ & - 0.742 \cdot F_{\text{rebuff}} - 0.106 \cdot T_{\text{rebuf}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, MOS_{avg} represents the image quality and the subtracted terms correspond to penalties for different factors affecting the user experience. Then, the proposed objective method can be summarized by the Equation (3), in the following:

$$QoE = \text{Quality}_{\text{image}} - \text{Penalties}_{\text{adaptive streaming}} \quad (3)$$

This formulation highlights the importance of a picture quality-centered approach, as measured by the Video-MOS solution, adjusted for the specific penalties of adaptive streaming. This provides a more comprehensive and accurate assessment of the user's quality of experience.

The QoE value reaches 5 when the $\text{Quality}_{\text{image}}$ parameter is 5 (the maximum quality estimated by the Video-MOS tool) and the contribution of the $\text{Penalties}_{\text{adaptive streaming}}$ is null (i.e., under ideal network and playback conditions). In contrast, the worst-case scenario can yield a QoE value of 1 (or even 0 or negative) when the MOS_{avg} is 1 (the minimum quality estimated by Video-MOS) and the contribution of the $\text{Penalties}_{\text{adaptive streaming}}$ parameter is positive. Since QoE is normalized between 1 to 5 following the MOS scale, any value below 1 is adjusted to 1. QoE value is highly dependent on the score obtained from the Video-MOS tool and is subsequently reduced as a function of the penalties. Conversely, the QoE value can never exceed the MOS_{avg} estimated by the tool.

C. ASSESSMENT OF IMAGE QUALITY AND PENALTIES IN ADAPTIVE STREAMING

For evaluating image quality, the commercial Video-MOS tool is employed. This Software as a Service (SaaS) solution utilizes MOS measurements to assess the image quality of specific video sequences. As a non-reference tool, it extracts features and parameters that enable both spatial and temporal characterization of the video content. Metrics such as SI, TI, sharpness, blocking artifacts, color fidelity, texture, brightness, and contrast are analyzed. Although Video-MOS SaaS solution was used in this study as a reference tool, the proposed method for QoE analysis is applicable to other MOS evaluation systems on the market.

The Video-MOS solution uses these comprehensive data to train AI-based nonlinear regression models, which estimate MOS values from the extracted features [9]. Regular assessments every 3 seconds capture the dynamic nature of adaptive streaming, providing a robust basis for subsequent QoE evaluations. By integrating these MOS values into the proposed model, the method aims to provide a precise and comprehensive assessment of the user's QoE in adaptive streaming environments.

An example of the Video-MOS tool's output for adaptive streaming across three different contents is shown in Fig. 4. It consists of an analysis of the MOS values for specific content at different resolutions and at different time intervals (Number of Measurements). The MOS value is obtained at each interval, meaning every three seconds, and these values are

considered throughout the entire video sequence. The quality values range from 1 to 5 according to the MOS scale defined in ITU-R BT.500-11 [8]. In the three video sequences, as the video resolution decreases, the MOS value also decreases. For the maximum video resolution (3840x2160), a quality value of 5 is not achieved due to the lossy encoding of the videos.

Each content presents its MPD with eight typical resolutions that maintain a 16:9 aspect ratio, which is common in a television signal. This ratio means that the width of the video in proportion to the height of the screen is 16:9 pixels, a default configuration in most devices due to its good performance.

To assess penalties, the DASH client *dash.js* is utilized. This client, a reference implementation created by the DASH Industry Forum (DASH-IF), enables the playback of adaptive videos using the MPEG-DASH standard with JavaScript⁵.

This client not only provides a standard implementation, but it has also been crucial in research and development for the T_{init} , F_{rebuf} and T_{rebuf} penalties methods. The client also allows us to analyze and evaluate the changes in content quality as a function of network conditions, which is vital for the implementation of the method.

According to the adopted model, three penalties have been defined as the most influential on the quality of experience. The way to calculate these values follows the structure of the following pseudocodes in Appendix A.

IV. RESULTS

Table 2 shows the QoE values for the three contents in the four scenarios. Additionally, it includes information on how penalties impact image quality as network conditions deteriorate. In this study, QoE is assessed using the MOS scale, which ranges from 1 to 5. Consequently, any computed QoE values below 1 are adjusted to this minimum threshold.

The QoE values obtained follow a consistent trend: optimal network condition reach higher QoE scores, while worsening network performance leads to a decline in QoE, reaching a minimum of 1 in extreme cases. The MOS values obtained in 2 serve as a baseline to calculate the QoE using the proposed equation (1).

Analyzing the average MOS values obtained using the Video-MOS tool for the three video content, it becomes apparent that *Big Buck Bunny* achieves the highest average MOS, indicating superior perceived quality. However, this content also exhibits the largest fluctuation between optimal and poor scenarios, with MOS values of 3.37 and 1.78, respectively, resulting in a variation of 1.59 points. The observed MOS fluctuations in *Big Buck Bunny* indicate a greater sensitivity to network conditions. However, this apparent sensitivity may also be affected by the accuracy of MOS estimation, requiring further validation through objective QoE metrics.

A reader might expect that all videos would achieve the maximum MOS score (5) under optimal network conditions.

⁵<https://reference.dashif.org/dash.js/nightly/samples/>

FIGURE 4. Output of the Video-MOS tool for three contents across different resolutions over time.

TABLE 2. Test Plan Results Overview

Content	Scenario	MOS_{avg}	T_{init} (s)	F_{rebuff} (1/s)	T_{rebuff} (%)	Total Penalty	QoE	Influence Total Penalty (%)
Big Buck Bunny	Optimal	3.37	0.01	0	0	0.01	3.36	0.40
	Good	2.94	0.04	0.0020	0.0035	0.04	2.90	1.46
	Acceptable	2.01	0.17	0.0010	0.0023	0.17	1.84	8.57
	Poor	1.78	1.41	0.0010	0.0023	1.41	$0.36 \approx 1$	79.63
Sintel	Optimal	3.14	0.02	0	0	0.03	3.12	0.59
	Good	3.04	0.03	0.0035	0.0008	0.03	3.01	0.96
	Acceptable	1.95	0.42	0.0015	0.0106	0.43	1.51	21.98
	Poor	1.76	1.40	0.0032	0.0075	1.41	$0.35 \approx 1$	80.01
Tears of Steel	Optimal	3.28	0.02	0	0	0.02	3.26	0.53
	Good	3.04	0.02	0.0008	0.0020	0.02	3.02	0.80
	Acceptable	1.98	0.40	0.0026	0.0060	0.40	1.57	20.51
	Poor	1.85	1.40	0.0008	0.0212	1.42	$0.43 \approx 1$	76.92

However, this is not always the case due to multiple factors, such as image artifacts and loss of quality because of video encoding processes.

In contrast, *Sintel* and *Tears of Steel* show relatively stable average MOS values. The difference in MOS values between the first two scenarios (optimal and good) is minimal, measuring 0.10 and 0.24 points, respectively. Similarly, when comparing the last two scenarios (acceptable and poor), the MOS scores show only slight decreases of 0.19 and 0.13 points, respectively. While all content experiences quality degradation due to network conditions and associated issues, the user experience with *Big Buck Bunny* is notably more affected.

Based on penalties, *Big Buck Bunny* remains relatively unaffected by varying network conditions when they are optimal, good, or acceptable but shows increased penalties (1.4174) when conditions are poor, suggesting general consistency. *Sintel* demonstrates the greatest stability in all scenarios tested with minimal changes. In contrast, *Tears of Steel* is the most susceptible to poor network conditions and exhibits a notable decline in perceived quality during severe degradation (1.4231).

The final column (influence total penalty) quantifies the relative impact of adaptive streaming mechanisms across different conditions. In optimal and good conditions, adaptive streaming is highly effective, with minimal variation in the average MOS and almost no buffering events, resulting in a

positive user experience (0.40%, 0.59%, 0.53%). However, in the acceptable scenario, penalties start to have a noticeable impact, and in the poor scenario, they become considerably severe. Expressing these penalties as percentages allows for a clearer comparison across conditions, highlighting the extent to which adverse network conditions amplify the gap between video quality and user experience, significantly degrading overall QoE.

The results of the tests reveal the effectiveness of this method in estimating the QoE and highlight F_{rebuff} as a crucial element. According to Mok's experiment, it is the parameter with the greatest influence on the user's experience, as reflected by the weight assigned to this factor in Equation (2) (0.7420). However, according to Table 2, it is not the major contributor in all cases. That is, although F_{rebuff} is the factor that bothers the user the most, the impact in absolute value on QoE also depends on the values of other parameters.

In particular, T_{init} , although it has a lower weight in the formula (0.0670), can become a more degrading factor for QoE when its value is significantly higher than the F_{rebuff} value. This is because, when T_{init} is high, its contribution to the QoE may be higher, even if its weight is lower, resulting in a more severe penalty.

Although the formula reflects that F_{rebuff} is the parameter most sensitive to small variations, when T_{init} is very long, it ends up having more impact on QoE, further degrading the user experience. Therefore, F_{rebuff} is the most influential

in relative terms, but in cases where T_{init} is high, the latter becomes the major contributor to the degradation of QoE.

Fig. 5 presents the distribution of resolution in percentages across the different network conditions, illustrating how adaptive streaming adjusts video quality in response to varying network performance. The data was collected using a single playback per video, providing insight into how the streaming algorithm dynamically selects resolution levels. As expected, under optimal network conditions, the highest resolutions are maintained for the majority of the playback, ensuring the best possible visual quality. However, as network conditions deteriorate, the adaptive streaming algorithm progressively reduces the resolution to prevent buffering and maintain smooth playback. This adaptation highlights the trade-off between video quality and playback stability, demonstrating the effectiveness of adaptive streaming mechanisms in mitigating the impact of poor network conditions.

Understanding the differences between MOS (image quality) and QoE (with the impact of network penalties) in these various contexts is especially important. Fig. 6 presents a comparison of MOS and QoE. While MOS mainly concerns the perception of image quality, whereas QoE includes additional factors such as latency and smoothness. This allows QoE to present a more extensive evaluation of the user's experience. Although MOS can fluctuate with changes in image quality, the influence on QoE depends on other factors that might minimize or amplify it. According to the figure, under optimal and good network conditions, there is negligible difference between QoE and MOS. However, as the network conditions worsen, the QoE values decrease substantially and increasingly diverge from MOS.

V. CONCLUSION

In this research, we developed an objective method to evaluate QoE in adaptive streaming by combining image quality metrics with network condition factors. Although this approach has been demonstrated with Video-MOS SaaS solution, it can be adapted to other MOS-based analysis tools, extending its use across different platforms. Our approach enhances the Mok model by using a dynamic QoE equation that factors in real-time video playback across different scenarios, taking into account initial load time, the frequency of rebuffering, and the duration of the interruption as detriments. This approach evaluates both image quality and playback stability, capturing factors that impact user experience.

Experiments carried out demonstrate the method's capability to estimate QoE, highlighting the rebuffering frequency as a main factor. Mok's experiment indicates that rebuffering frequency has the greatest influence on QoE, as reflected by its weight (0.7420) in the formula. However, it is not always the largest contributor in absolute terms. While rebuffering is the most annoying factor for users, the overall impact on QoE also depends on other parameters. Specifically, even though initialization time has a lower weight (0.0670), it can become a more significant factor when its value is much higher than rebuffering frequency, leading to a greater penalty on QoE.

Thus, while rebuffering is the most sensitive factor to small changes, a long initialization time can further degrade the user experience, making it the largest contributor in certain cases.

Additionally, the method has been verified to estimate the average image quality at different resolutions and to use this information to calculate the QoE, accounting for subjective parameters such as penalties due to buffering events. The impact of these subjective penalties on QoE, relative to the average MOS, has been evaluated, with penalties reaching up to 80% due to poor environment conditions. Notably, *Tears of Steel* exhibited the highest penalty under adverse conditions, with a MOS decrease of up to 1.42 points. In contrast, *Big Buck Bunny* showed the best QoE with a score of 3.36, while *Sintel* was the most stable, with a maximum MOS variation of only 0.49 between scenarios.

Although the three contents do not enable the creation of a generalized model for the method, this selection serves as a good starting point for its initial implementation. As further experiments are carried out with a wider variety of content, the approach can be validated and refined to develop a more robust and representative model.

Furthermore, the four scenarios were carefully selected to represent different network conditions that can impact the performance of adaptive streaming. In each scenario, the download speed is intentionally restricted to simulate varying degrees of network congestion, which impacts video playback quality. These scenarios were selected to reflect a range of real-world conditions, from optimal network performance to more challenging situations with limited bandwidth.

A. FUTURE WORK

After concluding this study, various enhancements were recognized to further this research and refine the suggested QoE analysis. Each proposal intends to get the method more comprehensive and beneficial, facilitating optimized content delivery and aligning more closely with user expectations.

The first future proposal considers enhancing the method's adaptability to make it suitable for the HLS standard on adaptive streaming. HLS and MPEG-DASH are presently the two predominant standards in adaptive streaming.

The present approach to QoE analysis relies on deriving an estimate of video quality by averaging MOS values collected at three-second intervals of video playback. Upcoming experiments will investigate the use of alternative statistical measures other than the average, for calculating the final MOS value, as well as varying the interval durations, with the aim of enhancing the final quality estimation. Related to this, we aim to adapt the method for use in real-time applications. Presently, the method requires pre-obtained MOS values for every available content resolution.

Future work also could explore QoE analysis using the implemented enhanced method with chunk sizes different from three seconds. This would help assess the performance of the solution under varying segmentation conditions and provide deeper insights into its adaptability and effectiveness. Also, while the current analysis relies on four fixed

FIGURE 5. Percentage distribution of resolutions across four quality scenarios for the contents.

FIGURE 6. Comparison of MOS and QoE across different quality scenarios for the contents.

network scenarios to evaluate QoE, future work could explore more dynamic testing environments where network conditions (e.g., bandwidth, latency, packet loss) fluctuate over time. This would better reflect real-world variability and provide a more comprehensive understanding of how adaptive streaming algorithms respond to dynamic changes.

While the current method effectively incorporates rebuffering frequency and time based on the Mok model to predict QoE, future efforts should focus on a deeper integration of network conditions surrounding the playback experience. This includes analyzing parameters such as throughput [40], latency [41], and packet loss [42] to capture their impact on QoE. In addition, including more advanced architectures with the integration of isolated link-layer networks, to refine the integration of network conditions [43]. Understanding these factors in conjunction with rebuffering events could enhance the precision of QoE estimation, helping to identify root causes behind penalties like rebuffering or quality degradation [44].

Additional work could further explore the relative impact of the factors in Mok model by analyzing the product of each coefficient and its respective parameter value. While rebuffering frequency has a higher theoretical weight, it is possible that its low actual values in the tested scenarios reduced its overall impact, whereas higher values of initialization time or rebuffering duration could dominate the total penalty.

Leveraging machine learning techniques could enable predictive QoE analysis [45], or even allowing proactive adjustments to avoid quality degradation such as reinforcement learning techniques [46], [47]. Furthermore, incorporating multi-modal data, such as user engagement or physiological responses, would further enrich the model by integrating insights into user behavior [48].

An additional factor for future consideration is the final QoE estimation. The current approach offers the QoE value only after the content has been fully playback. Future advancements will enable the possibility to measure the QoE by assessing the image quality and the impact of network penalties at user-defined intervals, thus enhancing the method's functionality.

All proposed future lines will be assessed through subjective experiments involving real observers. The tests will focus on examining the accuracy of the method implemented in this research, conducting experiments with the three contents presented under the conditions outlined in the four scenarios.

APPENDIX A PSEUDOCODE IMPLEMENTATIONS

Algorithm 1 Initial Buffer penalty

Require: clickEvent, playEvent, startTime \leftarrow 0, playTime \leftarrow 0, initialBuffer \leftarrow 0

```

if clickEvent then
    startTime  $\leftarrow$  getCurrentTime
end if
if playingEvent then
    playTime  $\leftarrow$  getCurrentTime
end if
if startTime  $\neq$  0 and playTime  $\neq$  0 then
    return (playTime - startTime) * 1000
else
    return 0
end if

```

Algorithm 2 Rebuffering frequency penalty

Require: videoDuration, bufferEmpty, bufferCounter \leftarrow 0, nRebuffering \leftarrow 0, RebufferingFrequency \leftarrow 0

```

Function RebufferingEvents()
if bufferEmpty then
    bufferCounter  $\leftarrow$  bufferCounter + 1
    if bufferCounter == 1 then
        nRebuffering  $\leftarrow$  nRebuffering + 1
    end if
else
    bufferCounter  $\leftarrow$  0
end if
return nRebuffering
End Function

loop
    nRebuffering  $\leftarrow$  RebufferingEvents()
    wait(3000)
end loop

```

return nRebuffering / videoDuration

Algorithm 3 Rebuffering period penalty

Require: bufferCount \leftarrow 0, totalPeriod \leftarrow 0, rebufferingPeriod \leftarrow 0, videoDuration

```

Function EmptyBufferPeriod()
if bufferEmpty then
    bufferCount  $\leftarrow$  bufferCount + 1
    totalPeriod  $\leftarrow$  totalPeriod + bufferCount * 3
else
    bufferCount  $\leftarrow$  0
end if
return totalPeriod
End Function

loop
    rebufferingPeriod  $\leftarrow$  EmptyBufferPeriod()
    wait(3000)
end loop

return totalPeriod / videoDuration

```

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⁷<https://www.video-mos.com/>

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